

Research

A Bacteria-Resistant Finish on Cellulose Fabric

Suraiya Sultana^{1,2*}, Tahmina Jahan¹

¹ Department of Textile Engineering, Port City International University, Chittagong, Bangladesh.

² School of Textile Science and Engineering, State Key Laboratory of New Textile Materials and Advanced Processing Technologies, Wuhan Textile University, China.

Abstract: When using fibers that naturally possess antibacterial qualities or have been treated to do so, fabric quality and strength are a concern. Innovative antibacterial fabrics have been produced by the textile industry to satisfy the need for personal protection against disease spread and improved cleanliness in the society. Attaching biocidal or bacteriostatic groups to the fabric surface has been the method used. Samples of the antimicrobial-treated cotton substrate were subjected to multiple items of washing before being tested in accordance with the textile evaluation for antibacterial activity standard (GB/T20944.1-2007). 100% plain-dyed cotton fabrics were pad-dried after being treated with various concentrations of a chemical agent based on RUKO BAC MED to achieve antibacterial efficacy. *Escherichia coli* and *staphylococcus aureus* are the two types of bacteria employed. Additionally, after washing, the treated fabric's durability and antibacterial activity efficacy will be assessed. Examine the chemical molecule homogeneity on the surface of the fiber using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and compare to untreated cloth. Using a scanning electron microscope, cotton fabric was utilized to examine the surface morphology of both the untreated and RUKO BAC MED treated fabrics by using Scanning Electron Microscope.

Keywords: Antibacterial, hygiene, Protection, *Escherichia coli*, *staphylococcus aureus*, surface morphology

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 13 May, 2023; **Published:** 14 June, 2023

How to cite this article: Suraiya, Tahmina (2023). A Bacteria-Resistant Finish on Cellulose Fabric. *North American Academic Research*, 6(5), 201-222. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8051480>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Antimicrobial treatment for disinfection materials is important to full fill the accompanying targets: to maintain a strategic distance from cross contamination by pathogenic microorganisms; to control the invasion by organisms; to capture digestion in microorganisms to decrease the arrangement smell; and to defend the material items from recoloring, staining and quality weakening. Material materials specifically, the pieces of fabricant are more helpless to wear and tear. It is essential to consider the effect of pressure strain, warm and mechanical consequences for the completed substrates. The accompanying prerequisites should be fulfilled to get most extreme advantages out of the complete: Durability to washing, cleaning and hot squeezing; particular movement to bothersome microorganisms; ought not deliver unsafe impacts to the producer, client and nature; ought to follow the statutory necessities of controlling organizations; similarity with the synthetic procedures; simple technique for application; no disintegration

of texture quality; impervious to body liquids; and impervious to sanitizations/cleansing. With respect to improvement of antimicrobial medicines for materials, the upsides of the picked antimicrobial specialist, for example, biocide adequacy, ought to exceed the potential natural outcomes and expenses of its use (1,2). As ecological advantages, antimicrobial-treated materials may display a delayed helpful time of material wear, the potential for less regular fabric cycles, bring down washing temperatures and a diminishment of cleanser utilization in each wash cycle. The most attractive operators are the ones that are at the same time proficient at low dosing levels and that present tough usefulness. The natural effect of the antimicrobial material, which is a basic (3).

The improvement of protection is a typical developmental process for microorganisms. But, this marvel is firmly quickened by the specific weight applied by across the board utilization of antibacterial medications, turning into an awesome worldwide general wellbeing worry of expanding greatness. Safe strains can proliferate and spread (4). Accordingly, the potential wellbeing impacts should be considered keeping in mind the end goal to assess the security of antimicrobial mixes for creatures and people. The sort of activity of the antimicrobial specialist, by dissemination or contact, its focus in the material, the introduction courses and the recurrence of utilization will impact the degree to which people might be presented to the material. A few parameters as a rule assessed to survey the hazard profile of an antimicrobial operator related with a material are the lethality (intense and interminable), skin refinement and aggravation and the unsettling influence of skin environment. For the majority of the antimicrobial specialists exhibited in this survey, there are

No assumptions with respect to their skin harmfulness and impacts on human wellbeing. On account of triclosan, its danger is a worry, as it is presumed that it might go about as an endocrine disrupter and has been seen to be conveyed in human tissues. On account of Si-QAC (silane quaternary ammonium mixes), as indicated by a few investigations, no extreme impact on human wellbeing was watched. On account of metallic mixes, ZnPT (zinc pyrithione), for example, may exhibit a few dangers of neurotoxicity (5). As to particles, which are non-particular in real life as different biocides, they may connect with skin verdure, causing the unit of the cytoplasmic film from the cell mass of solid microorganisms, debilitating the skin resistance obstruction (6). Besides, ceaseless contact with Ag can prompt testimony of Ag metal/Ag sulfide particles in skin, instigating its staining, known as argyria, or even visual staining, known as argyrosis. These are not dangerous conditions, but rather obviously, cosmetically bothersome (7).

Keeping in mind the end goal to impact the antimicrobials' utilization design and the piece of the overall industry of specific intensifies, a few changes in the material control ought to be performed. In this manner, the antimicrobial utilizes design in materials would be balanced by the particular application and need, bringing about a huge decrease of antimicrobials' stream to the earth. For example, the materials business utilizes the most elevated extent of aggregate utilized triclosan, while the utilization of QACs speaks to the minor extent of all utilized QACs. The 210 metric huge amounts of utilized triclosan in materials can be supplanted by either under two metric huge amounts of silver nanoparticles or by 180 metric huge amounts of Si-QAC, achieving comparable antimicrobial outcomes with a lower natural effect. Accordingly, the administrative evaluation of single antimicrobial substances ought to be founded on a more extensive point of view and information of antimicrobials, considering the dangers and advantages of their utilization contrasted with elective antimicrobial substances (8,9). An antimicrobial finish can be associated with most sorts of materials. A wide arrangement of antimicrobial fulfillments is at the present time being associated with nonwoven materials to be used as superfluous guarded bits of apparel in mending offices. Antimicrobial materials, paying little heed to whether woven, nonwoven, or sew, can in like manner be made out of a fiber content that is sensible for a bit of dress age. The fiber substance of an antimicrobial material must be picked absolutely. Fabricated surfaces may not be appropriate for some end uses in light of how most designed strands are

hydrophobic. This infers surfaces made of designed strands hold a greater measure of sweat wetness in their weave structures than do trademark fibers. This property can cause an extended shot of aggravation and fragrance on account of microbial advancement on the body (10).

The use of regular fibers is bolstered in light of the way that end-use things from ordinary strands are bio based, not petroleum based. Ordinary strands are moreover extraordinary hotspots for materials since they are reasonable resources and their admission can be helpful for a few economies. Cotton is plenteous and its mechanical properties are fitting for a piece of attire creation. It is definitely not hard to tend to and takes well to whitening. How a fiber reacts to kicking the bucket is basic while overseeing antimicrobial fruitions in light of the way that countless culminations require that the material is blurred to recuperate its antimicrobial properties. Both chlorine and oxygen blur are acceptable in restoring a materials antimicrobial finish as long as the best possible sort of color is used for the recuperation (11,12). Not all people are in support of antimicrobial agents. The medical industry is seeing a rise in the number of drug-resistant pathogens. This increase is most often attributed to the number of biocidal agents being used not only in hospitals but in homes and in the workplace. Antibacterial treatments are applied to a number of things that we use on a daily basis such as soaps, lotions, cleaning supplies, air conditioning and ventilation, materials for the food and pharmaceutical industries, and even construction materials. A common idea is that the increase in the number of antimicrobial agents used will heighten a person's susceptibility to infection. This notion is not far-fetched according to many doctors (13, 14). The inaccuracy of the idea occurs because many people attribute the use of antimicrobial agents to a decrease in the efficacy of an individual's immune system (15). In actuality, the use of antimicrobial agents supports the growth of drug-resistant strains of bacteria. One of the best-known antibiotic-resistant infections is methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) (16). This bacterium is known to be spread in hospitals through fabrics and by personal contact (7,8). According to Professors Christopher T. Walsh and Gerry Wright (17 p.392), "Given the vast numbers of bacteria, their short generation times, and typical gene mutation frequencies of 1 in 10⁷ bacteria resistance is inevitable. Antibiotics select for those very rare bacteria in a population that is less susceptible and allow them to become dominant in the populations as susceptible bacteria die off." So, resistance is unavoidable (18). The important question is whether or not you want to take action and kill the pathogens that come into contact with, or just allow nature to take its course and immune system do all the work. The proposed research investigates the procedure for execution antimicrobial treatment to the textile materials, which implicates the crosslinking between the compound and the textile substrate (19). Also, the study aims to determine the effect of the crosslinking of antimicrobial agent to the textile substrate on the antimicrobial effectiveness, washing durability, and comfort properties and analyze their effects. Determination the bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* can grow and reduction from the fabric by using agar plate diffusion (Qualitative) and bacteria reduction method (Quantitative) test for antibacterial finishes in the fabric (20,21).

The purpose of this research is to determine if an antimicrobial finish that is effective against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* will be active for up to 10 home launderings (22,23). To improve Antibacterial and anti-allergenic (dust mites) finishing for all Cotton fabric worn next to the skin. Find out bacteriocidal and slightly fungicidal properties avoids the development of dust mites resistant to elevated drying temperatures. This research will deliver useful evidence on woven, reusable, antimicrobial cotton fabrics that will be helpful to the daily life, medical industry and the general community(24,25). The presence of antimicrobial agents keeps the textiles fresh and avoids odor, and is suitable for use in areas that are in direct contact with the skin. This work has done change of Anti-Bacterial capacity by a hostile to Bacterial operator. Antimicrobial materials are effortlessly come about a place in the worldwide material market. Their end uses can be customized to fit the requirements of numerous different individuals and their callings. Most antimicrobial experimentation is being performed for the therapeutic business.

The attire business can profit by this examination on the grounds that the items made for the two callings are firmly related. The quantity of sheltered and strong antimicrobial completions is step by step developing. A significance is being put on the utilization of textures made of characteristic filaments in light of the fact that the world economy is attempting to diminish the general utilize and generation of issue free-based items (manufactured strands). The worldwide pattern for a more secure condition is obvious surrounding us.

Materials and Methods

This dissertation introduces and discusses a hypothesis aimed at durable antibacterial treatment on cotton fabric by using chemical concentration. The bacteria *Escherichia coli* (Gram negative) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive) were used. Mainly focused on applying various percentage (%) of concentration to find out best lower amount of percentage and observe the existence of chemicals after several times washing effects. For acquiring the best results applying different types of method.

Materials

In this experiment, 100 % plain cotton fabric was obtained from Hunan Huasheng Zhuzhou Cedar Company, (China). The Chemical ®RUCO-BAC MED were taken directly from Rudolf Chemie Co., Ltd. (China), and the dyes were commercial grade, purchased from the Shanghai Jiaying Chemical Company, (China). All the raw materials and machines such as, acetic acid, ECE soaping, and tryptone, yeast extract, sodium chloride (NaCl), agar powder (bacteria solution and culture medium), bacterium; *Escherichia coli* (AATCC 4352) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (AATCC 6538), etc. were taken from Engineering Research Centre for Clean Production of Textile Dyeing & Printing, Ministry of Education lab. In this dissertation were also used so many machines such as, high temperature and high-pressure machine, dyeing machine (HTX-12, Huaxia Technology Company, China), air dry machine, pad-dry machine, K/S value test machine, padding machine, QYC-211 Full-Temperature Culture Shaker (CIMO) machine (China), test tube, high pressure sterilization machine, incubator machine and so on. Analytical Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) machine (JSM IT300A, JEOL Ltd, Japan) were used from Material Science and Engineering department lab. Water used in all experiments was purified using a Milli-Q Plus 185 water purification system (Millipore, Bedford, MA) with a resistivity higher than 18 MX cm.

Methodology

Fabric Preparation

100% plain cotton fabric roll received from the laboratory. Make sure about the cleanliness of the fabric. Cutted into several pieces as A4 size (8inch x 11inch) and mark it for counting. After all, made suitable for a further stage like dyeing.

Dyeing of Cotton fabric with Reactive dyes

Dyeing recipe: 100% cotton fabric dyed with the reactive orange 5. The A4 size fabric was taken total 8 samples, Dye mass: 3% o.m.f., Salt (NaCl): 40 g/L, Caustic Soda (Na₂CO₃): 10 g/L, Liquor ratio: 1:15.

Dyeing process: Fabric and dye stuff put together in small dyeing bath with the room temperature for 15 min, add Salt (NaCl) for increasing affinity. again machine run for 15 min and increasing temperature until reached 60°C. pour Sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃) for fixation and continue running for 30 min. After that, decreased the temperature until reached 30°C. Take out the all fabric and dry at 70-90°C.

Washing Process of cotton dye

To remove the natural impurities, residual auxiliaries, contamination etc. Soaping for all samples with 2 g/L of non-ionic soaping detergent at 70°C for 10 min at a liquor ratio of 1:10. Take out the specimen and finally rinsed with cold water and dried in hot air oven at 120°C.

Figure 1: Dyeing curve of Cotton dyeing with Reactive dye.

Deposition of antibacterial treatment in dyed cotton fabric through pad-dry

Padding Process: The antibacterial chemical has been applied on dyed cotton fabric after dyeing to improve the antimicrobial performance and protecting durability and reuseable of cotton fabric. The antibacterial chemical was diluted with distilled water at different concentration. Maintain the PH value 5-6. Then dyed cotton fabric was sunk into antibacterial solution and pass through the padding machine roller. In padding roller, the bar pressure was kept at 2.5 bar and temperature was normal. Maximus pick up range was 70 %. Finally, samples were rinsed with cold water and dried in an oven at 120°C. Pick-up% are followed by below the equation,

$$\text{Pickup\%} = \frac{\text{After Fabric Weight} - \text{Before Fabric Wight}}{\text{Before Fabric Wight}} \times 100$$

Then the sample was soaped with 2 g/L detergent for 15 min at 60°C at a liquor ratio of 1:10, and finally rinsed with cold water and dried in hot air oven at 120°C.

Experimental Part of anti-bacterial

Prepare the fabric: Fabrics are treated with the concentration of 20 g/L, 30 g/L, 40 g/L, 50 g/L, 60 g/L (for *Escherichia coli*) and (for *Staphylococcus aureus*) and kept an untreated fabric for comparison. After that each fabric was cut into round small pieces with the weight of around 0.2 gm.

Bacterial culture

Materials for culture medium: For Preparing the culture medium 100 ml, tryptone (Tryptone) 10 g/L, yeast extract (Yeast extract) 5 g/L, sodium chloride (NaCl) 10 g/L, and agar powder: 15-20 g/L mixed with distilled water.

Materials for culture solution

For preparing culture solution 100 ml, tryptone (Tryptone) 10 g/L, yeast extract (Yeast extract) 5 g/L, and sodium chloride (NaCl) 10 g/L mixed with distilled water.

Pre-Sub experimental work of E. Coli.

The Initial Passage of E. coli Experimental materials: Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus aureus with sterile water contains in a bottle, toothpick, cone bottle, and 120ml bacteria culture liquid were removed from the freezer at -72°C

Process: Distil water, toothpick, cone bottle and culture liquid were sterilized for 2 hr at 121°C. The tweezers, alcohol lamps and alcohol cotton are placed in the super net to open the ultraviolet lamp for 20 min, and the experimental products are placed in the autoclave cooker. The aseptic water and the culture liquid were cooled down to start the experiment. The hands and tweezers are wiped with alcohol cotton, and the alcohol lamp is ignited. The toothpick is dipped in the liquid preserved in propanol and the toothpick is placed in the culture of the conical bottle. Putted into the conical bottle in the rocking bed for 24 hr.

Secondary Passage of E. coli

Preparation: The vial of sterile water, toothpicks, Erlenmeyer flasks, culture solutions, and test tubes were sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 2 hr. The tweezers, alcohol lamps, and alcohol cotton in a clean bench placed and turn on the UV light for the sterilization for 20 min. Started the experiment process after the sterilized water and the culture solution were cooled down. Wipe hands and materials with alcohol cotton and light the alcohol lamp. The nutrition broth was poured into three tubes on average. The bacteria solution was picked up after 24 h with a toothpick, and the toothpick was placed in the bacteria culture of the test tube. Marked that three test tubes. Placed the three tubes in a constant temperature shaker for 24 hr.

Procedure: Placed 120 ml of solid medium, sterile water, 2 types of pipette tips, 1 ml centrifuge tube, 6 spreaders, and 6 Petri dishes in an autoclave for sterilizing at 121°C for 2 hr. Turn on the ultra-violet light. Before the experiment place the pipette, alcohol lamp, alcohol cotton in the ultra-clean bench and after 20 min the solid medium liquid is poured into 12 Petri dishes on average, and it is allowed to cool and solidify. Dilute the original broth tube no. 1 to 108 times, dilute it in a gradient, ten times for each dilution. Take 0.9 ml of sterile water in a centrifuge tube with a pipette, and then use a pipette to take 0.1 ml of the bacteria original. The bacterial solution in the centrifuge tube marked as 1 and then using a pipette to take 0.9 ml of water and the centrifuge tube labeled 2 and take 0.1ml of the diluted bacterial solution in the No. 1 centrifuge tube and in the No. 2 centrifuge tube, successively diluted. Take 0.025 ml of bacterial solution in 106, 107, and 108 cells concentration. Prepare two plates for each concentration. Twelve plates were placed in a 37°C incubator for 24 hr.

Bacteria counts calculation procedure:

View the growth of E. coli in the six Petri dishes. If there is no contamination then count the single colonies. Count the number of colonies in the twelve Petri dishes and calculate the concentration of E. coli in the no. 1 test tube according to the formula. Example for 106 times. $C1 = ((c1+c2)/2)$. The average value of the two, if the concentration is between 105 and 108/ml that could be used as the experimental bacterium solution for the next experiment. The concentration of the broth in No. 1 test tube was 3×10^8 CFU/ml, which can be used as the experimental broth for the next experiment.

Pre-sub trial work of Staphylococcus aureus

The initial passage of Staphylococcus aureus

Materials: Staphylococcus aureus were collected from the refrigerated freezer at -72 °C and for making solution need sterile water, toothpick, Erlenmeyer flask, 120ml culture solution.

Procedure: Sterilize water, toothpicks, Erlenmeyer flask, and culture solution are put in an autoclave at 121°C for 2 hr. Placed the tweezers, alcohol lamp, and alcohol cotton in a clean bench and turn on the UV lamp for 20 min and place the test article in the autoclave. Started the experiment after the sterilized water and the culture solution are cooled down. Wipe the two hands and tweezers with alcohol cotton for removing existing bacteria, ignite the alcohol lamp, use a toothpick to pick up the bacteria solution stored in the propanol, and place the toothpick in the culture solution on a conical flask. Place the flask in a shaker and incubate for 24 hr.

Secondary passage of Staphylococcus aureus

Materials: Requirement materials are Vial sterile water, Toothpick, Erlenmeyer flask, 90 ml nutrition solution, three test tubes, and Bacterial liquid.

Procedure: The vial of sterile water, toothpicks, Erlenmeyer flasks, nutrition solution, and test tubes were sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 2 hr. Place tweezers, alcohol lamps, and alcohol cotton in a clean bench and turn on the UV lamp for 20 min. Start the experiment after the sterilized water and broth are cooled down. Then, ignite the alcohol lamp and pour the LB broth into the three test tubes on average. The broth after 24 hr of culture was picked up with a toothpick, and the toothpick was placed in the LB broth of test tube. Mark three test tubes. Place the three tubes in a constant temperature shaker for 24 hr.

Bacteria solution coating culture

Materials: Solid medium 120 ml, sterile water, pipette tips, 1ml centrifuge tubes, six coating sticks, six Petri dishes, and nutrition broth.

Procedure: Placed 120 ml of solid medium, sterile water, 2 types of pipette tip, 1 ml centrifuge tube, 6 spreaders, and 6 Petri dishes in an autoclave and sterilize at 121°C for 2 hr. Before the experiment place the pipette, alcohol lamp, alcohol cotton in the clean bench and pour the solid medium liquid into the 12 Petri dishes on average then turn on the ultra-violet UV light for 20 min. Wait till Cooled and solidified. Dilute the original broth in tube No. 1 to 108 times. Dilute it in a serial manner. Dilute it ten times. Use a pipette to take 0.9 ml of sterile water in a centrifuge tube. Use a pipette to take 0.1 ml of the original. Bacterial solution in the centrifuge tube, marked as 1, and then using a pipette to take 0.9 ml of water and the centrifuge tube labeled as 2 and take 0.1ml of the diluted bacterial solution in the No. 1 centrifuge tube and No. 2 centrifuge tube, successively diluted and take 0.025 ml of bacterial solution in 106, 107, and 108 cells concentration. Apply two plates for each concentration of 12 plates were placed in a 37°C incubator for 24 hr.

Bacteria counts calculation procedure:

View the growth of Staphylococcus aureus in the six Petri dishes. If there is no contamination then, count the single colonies. Count the number of colonies in the twelve Petri dishes and calculate the concentration of Staphylococcus aureus in the No. 1 test tube according to the formula. Example 106 times, $C1 = ((c1+c2)/2)$. The average value of the three, if the concentration is between 105 and 108/ml, can be used as the experimental bacterium solution for the next experiment. Experimental results the concentration of the broth in No. 1 test tube was 2.5×10^8 CFU/ml, which could be used as the experimental broth for the next experiment.

Characterizations

K/s color strength measurement

To evaluate dyeing performance, the color strength (K/S) and CIELAB of the dyed samples were measured using a Data color 110 spectrophotometers with illuminant D65 and 100 observer. The K/S is calculated by the Kubelka–

Munk equation, $K/S = (1 - R)^2/2R$, where R is the reflectance, K is the absorption coefficient, and S is the scattering coefficient. The color difference is expressed as ΔE_x and is calculated by the following

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{(\Delta L^*)^2 + (\Delta a^*)^2 + (\Delta b^*)^2}$$

where ΔE_x is the CIELAB color difference between batch and standard. Here ΔL_x , Δa_x , Δb_x and hence ΔE_x are incommensurate units. ΔL_x denotes the difference between lightness (where $L_x = 100$) and darkness (where $L_x = 0$), Δa_x the difference between green ($-a_x$) and red ($+a_x$) and Δb_x the difference between yellow ($+b_x$) and blue ($-b_x$) [74].

All measured samples showed a maximum absorption wavelength value (λ_{max}) at 421 nm. The colorfastness to washing, light, crocking of the dyed samples were determined according to AATCC Test Method 61-2010, ISO 105-B02: 1994, and AATCC Test Method 8-2007 respectively.

Figure-2: CIELAB color space.

Test process qualitative (AATCC method;147, agar diffusion Plate Test) and quantitative (AATCC 100-2004, flask Shaking Method)

Qualitative test process for Escherichia Coli

Materials selection: Antibacterial fabric were divided into six groups, the first group of fabrics are without antibacterial treatment, and the second group to the sixth group were treated with 20 g/L, 30 g/L, 30 g/L, 40 g/L, 50 g/L, 60 g/L treatment liquid.

Qualitative experiment

Preparation: Cut into six groups of circular fabrics. Placed a fabric in the middle of the two Petri dishes and place the six groups of fabric in the middle of the petri dishes. The prepared fabric and culture medium, 6 petri dishes, spreader bar, pipette tip, centrifuge tube, and vial of distilled water were placed in sterilized machine for 2 hr at 121°C. Turn on the ultra-violet light and place the pipette, alcohol lamp, and alcohol cotton in the clean bench for 20 min. Start the experiment before operating the alcohol lamp. The solid medium liquid was poured into 6 petri dishes on average, waiting for cooling and solidification, and the UV light was turned on for sterilization during the process. The broth in No. 1 test tube was diluted with sterile water to a concentration of 3×10^5 CFU/ml as a test broth, and 0.03 ml of the test bacteria was pipetted into the culture medium with a pipette and the broth was smeared with a spreader. Evenly, all 6 media were operated and numbered 1 to 6. Laid 1~6 fabrics in the middle of 1~6 solution medium. The culture medium was placed in a constant temperature incubator and incubated at 37°C for 24 hr.

Qualitative test process for *Staphylococcus aureus*

Materials Selection: Antibacterial treated fabric, divided into five groups, the first group of fabrics without antibacterial treatment, the second group to the fifth group were treated with 20 g/L, 30 g/L, 40 g/L, 50 g/L, 60 g/L treatment liquid.

Qualitative experiment

Preparation: Cut into six groups of circular fabrics, and prepare the following articles, 120 ml medium, 13 Petri dishes, 6 spreader rods, pipette gun tips, 1 bottle of *Staphylococcus aureus* solution, centrifuge tube and a small bottle of distilled water. Place a fabric in the middle of the two Petri dishes and place the six groups of fabric in the middle of Petri dishes. The prepared fabric and culture medium, 6 Petri dishes, spreader bar, pipette tip, centrifuge tube, and a vial of distilled water were sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 2 hr. Place the pipette, alcohol lamp, and alcohol cotton in the clean bench for 20 min and turn on the ultra-violet light before the experiment and start the experiment before operating the lit alcohol lamp. The solid medium liquid was poured into 6 Petri dishes on average, waiting for cooling and solidification and the UV light was turned on for sterilization during the process. The nutrition broth in No. 1 test tube was diluted with sterile water to a concentration of 2.5×10^5 CFU/ml as a test broth, and 0.03 ml of the test bacteria was pipetted into the culture medium with a pipette and the broth was smeared with a spreader. Evenly, all 6 media were operated and numbered 1 to 6. Laid 1~6 fabrics in the middle of 1~6 medium. The culture medium was placed in a constant temperature incubator and incubated at 37°C for 24 hr.

Quantitative test process for *Escherichia Coli*

Preparation: Cut the experimental fabric to round shape with the weight of 0.2 gm and number the fabric. The fabric that was not treated with the test solution was designated as the control group number 1 and the rest numbers 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6. The filter paper is cut into a circle and placed on the bottom of the conical flask, the fabric is placed on the filter paper in the conical flask, and the conical flask is marked as 1 to 6 in order. Erlenmeyer flasks filled with fabric, broth, vials of sterile water, centrifuge tubes, pipette tips, Petri dishes, were sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 2 hr. Place the pipette, alcohol, and alcohol cotton in the clean bench for 20 min before the experiment. Disinfect the hands with alcohol cotton, ignite the alcohol lamp, and operate it in front of the alcohol lamp. Dilute the broth in No. 1 test tube with sterile water to a concentration of 3×10^5 CFU/ml as the test broth and clip the Erlenmeyer flask out of the Erlenmeyer flask. The fabric is placed in the culture solution and infiltrated with 0.5 ml of sterile water to wet the filter paper in the conical flask. The infiltrated fabric is put back into the conical flask and 0.03 ml of the experimental bacteria is dropped into the conical flask. On the fabric (do not drop in one place, drop a drop everywhere). The fabrics in the six conical flasks are operated like this, the 6 conical flasks were incubated in a constant temperature incubator at 37°C for 24 hr. Bacteriostatic activity of colloidal solution was evaluated after certain contact time and calculated percent reduction of bacteria. Using following equation-

$$R\% = (A - B) / A \times 100$$

Where, R = the reduction rate, A = the number of bacterial colonies from untreated fabrics, and B = the number of bacterial colonies from treated fabrics.

Quantitative test process for *Staphylococcus aureus*

Materials selection: Untreated control group, fabric treated with 20 g/L, 30 g/L, 40 g/L, 50 g/L, 60 g/L antibacterial chemical solution.

Experimental preparation: Fabric, nutrition broth, vials of sterile water, six conical flasks, filter paper, tip, forceps, petri dish 1. The fabric that was not treated with the test solution was designated as the control group No. 1, and the remaining were designated as 2, 3, 4, and 5. The filter paper is cut into a circle and placed on the bottom of the conical flask, the fabric is placed on the filter paper in the conical flask and the conical flask is marked as 1 to 5 in sequence. Erlenmeyer flasks filled with fabric, nutrition broth, vials of sterile water, centrifuge tubes, pistol tips, Petri dishes, were sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 2 hr. Turn on the ultra-violet light and place the pipette, alcohol, and alcohol cotton in the clean bench for 20 min. Ignite the alcohol lamp and operate it in front of the alcohol lamp. Dilute the broth in no. 1 tube with sterile water to a concentration of 2.5×10^5 CFU/ml as the experimental broth. Tweezers of the fabric in the Erlenmeyer flask and place it on the culture broth. Infiltration wet the filter paper in the Erlenmeyer flask with 0.5 ml of sterile water, place the soaked fabric back into the flask, and place 0.03 ml of the test bacteria on the fabric in the conical flask. The fabrics in the six conical flasks are operated like this, the 6 conical flasks were incubated in a constant temperature incubator at 37°C for 24 hr. Bacteriostatic activity of colloidal solution was evaluated after certain contact time and calculated percent reduction of bacteria. Using following equation-

$$R\% = \frac{A-B}{A} \times 100$$

Where, R = the reduction rate, A = the number of bacterial colonies from untreated fabrics, and B= the number of bacterial colonies from treated fabrics.

Washing durability test process

Washing Process for Quantitative test (Escherichia Coli)

Fabric Selection: From fabric selected 60 g/L treatment solution of the fabric for washing durability test. Choose five fabrics, and one fabric did not wash. The second fabric was washed once in the clear water and dried naturally. The third fabric was washed twice in the clear water, dried naturally each time, and the fourth fabric was washed three times, each time naturally dried. The fifth fabric was washed four times and dried naturally every time.

Process: Same as the Qualitative test process for Staphylococcus aureus.

Washing process for quantitative test (Staphylococcus Aureus)

Fabric Selection: From fabric selected 60 g/L treatment solution of the fabric for washing durability test.

Choose five fabrics, and one fabric did not wash for comparison. The second fabric was washed once in the clear water and dried naturally. The third fabric was washed twice in the clear water, dried naturally each time, and the fourth fabric was washed three times, each time naturally dried. The fifth fabric was washed four times and dried naturally every time.

Process: Same as the content of Quantitative test process for Staphylococcus aureus

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) test

The surface of two groups of cotton fabric, group 1, untreated and group 2, treated with the concentration of 50 g/L and 60 g/L cotton fabric were observed using a Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (JSM IT300A, JEOL Ltd, Japan) with an operating voltage of 30 kV. Prior to SEM observation, samples were first glued onto a conducting resin and then sputter coated with Pt films with a thickness of 10 nm. In SEM scans the surface of the material and projects the image of the material's topography on a computer screen. SEM uses a beam of electrons which hits the surface and generates secondary electron with a low energy of 50eV. The secondary electrons were detected by an Everhart Thornley detector and the final image was projected on a computer screen. The bright spots are caused due to a large

number of electrons escaping from the surface while dark spots are caused due to the escaping of a small number of electrons.

Results and Data Analysis

K/S value investigation

Color strength always defines the ability of dyes or pigment to change the color of a colorless material. The lower the concentration of a colored pigment required to achieve a defined impression of color that is a given depth of a shade, the greater is the color strength of colored pigments. It depends on the absorption coefficient (K) of colorant. The higher the absorption coefficient, the higher will be the strength of colorants. The strength of any colorant (dyestuff/pigment) is related to absorption property.

Table 1: K/S value of Cotton fabric before treated (without an antibacterial agent)

Sample	L	A	B	$\Delta Exab$	K/S(520nm)
1	49.04	55.58	30.69	1.14	11.72
2	49.15	56.05	30.79	0.71	11.71
3	48.78	56.27	31.01	0.62	12.22
4	47.85	56.07	30.75	1.64	12.80
5	49.31	56.12	30.79	0.59	11.74
6	48.93	55.59	30.71	1.13	11.96

Table 1: K/S value of Cotton after treated by antibacterial agent

Sample	L	A	B	$\Delta Exab$	K/S(520nm)
1	47.48	53.20	26.16	0.97	11.24
2	47.15	51.35	24.58	1.63	10.68
3	47.19	52.49	25.85	0.73	11.28
4	46.38	53.09	25.67	1.07	11.84
5	47.42	52.81	25.62	0.34	11.03

Evaluation of K/s value

The a value shown as shown in Table 1 and 2 indicate that all the sample are green tone. The b values showed that the sample is bluer. L values indicate that the sample has bright shade. It is clear from the table that there is no considerable difference in L, a, b, c value for both. Moreover, the variation in concentration of anti-bacterial agent does not affect color tone at same dyes shade (3%) and a, b, $\Delta Exab$ are almost constant. The value varies slightly when the concentration of antibacterial agent is increased from 0-3%. But That means there is no significant contrast Color difference between before treated and after treated. So Anti Bacteria Agent does not effect color in cotton dyed Fabric.

Analysis of antimicrobial activity

The first method of evaluation of antimicrobial efficacy was qualitative analysis for the presence of antimicrobial activity of treated fabrics. The second method was quantitative analysis to determine percentage reduction in bacteria on treatment by the different antimicrobial agents.

Qualitative calculation and analysis

The qualitative evaluation was done as per AATTC Test Method 30-2004 antifungal activity, assessment of textile materials: Mildew and rot resistance of textiles: Test III agar plate test, aspergillus niger. The mean zones of inhibition (ZOI) were calculated for the substrates treated with RUKO BAC MED substrates were zero since they are bound antimicrobial agents and this method works best for controlled release antimicrobial agents.

Table 3: Table of inhibition of RUKO BAC MED treated cotton against Escherichia-coli.

Concentration (g/L)	Fabric Diameter (mm)	Inhibition area (mm)	Growth under sample
20	49.9	57	None
30	49.9	60	None
40	50.8	59.2	None
50	50.1	59.4	None
60	49.7	61.7	None
untreated	50		Too much

Figure 3: A graphical presentation of treated fabric diameter and effected inhabitation area in mm.

Table 2: Table of inhibition of RUKO BAC MED treated cotton against Staphylococcus aureus.

Concentration(g/L)	Fabric Diameter (mm)	Inhibition area (mm)	Growth under sample
20	49.9	0	None
30	49	0	None
40	50	0	None
50	47	53.6	None
60	48	58.6	None
untreated	-	-	Too much

Figure 4: illustrative photographs are displayed zone of inhibition of RUKO BAC MED cotton fabric against *Escherichia coli* : after treatment (Concentration:20 g/L-60 g/L) and before treatment.

Figure 5: Illustrative photographs are displayed zone of inhibition of RUKO BAC MED cotton fabric against *S. Aureus*: after treatment (Concentration: 20 g/L-60 g/L) and before treatment.

Figure 6: A graphical presentation of treated fabric diameter and effected inhabitation area in mm.

Qualitative analysis

In Qualitative Analysis, As the data show, RUKO BAC MED was not a too much effective antimicrobial agent against Staphylococcus aureus compare to Escherichia coli. it exhibited in Staphylococcus aureus 20 g/L-40 g/L did not create inhabitation area where created inhabitation area for 20 g/L-40 g/L in case of Escherichia coli . So eventually, it can expressed that RUKO BAC MED has good antibacterial activity against Escherichia coli.

Quantitative evaluation and analysis

Quantitative evaluation was carried out as per AATCC test method 100: Antibacterial finishes on textile materials. These methods allowed an accurate determination of the percentage of microbial growth inhibition in RUKO BAC MED treated Cotton fabric. The percent reduction of bacteria was calculated using equation:

$$R\% = \frac{A-B}{A} \times 100$$

Here, R=Per cent reduction of bacteria, A = The number of bacteria on the untreated fabric after 24 hr. B = the number of bacteria on the antibacterial treated fabric after 24 hr.

Table 5: Percentage reduction of bacteria for RUKO BAC MED treated cotton against Escherichia coli.

Concentration % (g/L)	CFUxNo. Of Dulite	Reduction of bacteria, %
20	9x10 ² and 4x10 ³	87
30	3x10 ² and 0x10 ³	98.58
40	0x10 ² and 0x10 ³	100
50	0x10 ² and 0x10 ³	100
60	0x10 ² and 0x10 ²	100
Untreated	106 and 25	-

Figure 7: A graphical presentation of reduction bacteria rate in RUKO BAC MED treated fabric Escherichia-coli.

Table 6: Percentage reduction of bacteria for RUKO BAC MED treated cotton S. Aureus.

Concentration % (g/L)	CFUxNo. Of Dulite	Reduction of bacteria, %
20	8x10 ² and 39x10 ³	59.19
30	12x10 ² and 10x10 ³	83.50
40	0x10 ² and 0x10 ³	100
50	0x10 ² and 0x10 ³	100
60	0x10 ² and 0x10 ²	-
Untreated	121 and 52	-

Figure 8: A graphical presentation of reduction bacteria rate in RUKO BAC MED treated fabric S. Aureus.

Figure 9: Illustrative photographs are displayed zone of the reduction rate of RUKO BAC MED treated cotton fabric against Escherichia coli (Concentration:60 g/L) and without treatment (Before Wash).

Quantitative Analysis

A Quantitative analysis, RUKO BAC MED possessed excellent antimicrobial activity against Escherichia coli with 100% reduction as well as Staphylococcus aureus against with a reduction of 100% (Table 5 and 6). The table and graph shows that the reduction rate of in E.coli and S. Aureus was vary in different concentration. Against Escherichia coli in 20 g/L,30 g/L the reduction rate decrease. The reduction rate of Bacteria is satisfactory. On the other hand, In S. Aureus in 20 g/L and 30 g/L shows reduction rate is high. But when increasing the concentration of anti-bacterial agent it shows that reduction rate is also satisfactory.

Quantitative evaluation and analysis (After multiple washes)

The wash durability of anti-Bacterial activity of the dyed sample was evaluated after the different wash cycle. Washed sample was tested for retention of Anti-Bacterial activity after 2,4,6 and 8 Laundering to evaluate the efficiency of anti-Bacterial action.

Figure 10: Illustrative photographs are displayed quantitative view of RUKO BAC MED treated cotton fabric against Escherichia coli (Concentration: 60 g/L) and without treatment (after multiple time wash).

Table 7: Percentage reduction of bacteria for RUKO BAC MED treated cotton Escherichia-coli.

Concentration % (g/L)	laundry cycles	CFUxNo. Of Dilute	Reduction of bacteria %
60	0 Wash	0x10 ² and 0x10 ³	100
	2 Wash	0x10 ² and 0x10 ³	100
	4 Wash	0x10 ² and 0x10 ³	100
	6Wash	14x10 ² and 10x10 ³	94.14
	8 Wash	20x10 ² and 15x10 ³	91.32
Untreated	-	442x10 ² and 117x10 ³	-

Figure 11: A graphical presentation of reduction bacteria rate in RUKO BAC MED treated fabric with Escherichia-coli (after wash).

Figure 12: A graphical reduction rate of bacteria of RUKO BAC MED treated fabric against Staphylococcus aureus (after wash).

Quantitative Analysis

In the Quantitative analysis, RUKO BAC MED was equally effective against Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus aureus at 0 wash cycle (without a wash) with 100% and 100% reduction respectively (Table 7 and 8). After 2, 4 wash cycle the antibacterial effectiveness did not change. The activity against Escherichia coli remained high decreasing to 94.12% after 6 wash cycles and 91.32 after 8 wash cycle. In Escherichia coli, the performance shows that even after 8 wash it maintain antibacterial properties activity. So RUKO BAC MED is excellent for Escherichia coli. On the other hand, a variation of concentration of anti-bacterial agent does not affect in a rate reduction of Bacteria for S. Aureus. The efficacy against Staphylococcus aureus however reduced significantly to 67% after 8 wash cycles. So in Staphylococcus aureus, the data shows that RUKO BAC MED has still antibacterial efficiency after 8 Wash.

Figure 13: Illustrative photographs are displayed quantitative view of RUKO BAC MED treated cotton fabric against Staphylococcus aureus (Concentration:60 g/L) and without treatment (after multiple time wash).

Table 8: Percentage reduction of bacteria for RUKO BAC MED treated cotton Staphylococcus aureus.

Concentration (g/L)	Number of the laundry cycle	No. Of Bacteria	Reduction of bacteria, %
60	0	0x2	100
	0	0x3	100
	2	0x2	100
	2	Ab	100
	4	0x10 ²	99.6
	4	3x10 ³	99.6
	6	577x10 ²	76.836
	6	20x10 ³	76.836
	8	76x10 ²	67.12
	8	423x10 ³	67.12

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Suraiya Sultana

She is now employed as a Senior lecturer of Textile Engineering department at Port City International University, Chittagong, Bangladesh. Her core research direction at present-day: textile product structure and performance research; textile new material development and solicitation and textile product design; functional textile expansion, Polymer Chemistry, Nanotechnology, Nano Materials, and Chemistry.

Tahmina Jahan

She is currently working as a Senior lecturer of Textile Engineering department at Port City International University, Chittagong, Bangladesh. Key research track at current; Dyeing, Wet processing, textile chemicals, natural fiber.

